

Feasibility of DC current commutation in capacitive circuit with 12kV DC CB

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Abstract—This paper investigates the feasibility of current commutation into capacitive branch in a 12 kV LC DC circuit breaker (CB). Specifically, parasitic parameters in the commutation loop are identified, measured and analyzed. Two analytical models are developed: a capacitor discharge model used to extract parasitic parameters and commutation model for evaluating current transfer under arc voltage. The experimental tests on commercial Medium Voltage (MV) capacitors and busbars provide realistic input data for parameter identification. The study evaluates the commutating current, arc voltage and arcing time, which are important for developing commercial DC CB. Results confirm that passive commutation might be feasible in 12 kV DC CB, but depends on the performance of ultrafast disconnector and safety margins.

Keywords—DC Circuit Breaker, Commutation circuit model, Pre-charged capacitor, Parasitics

I. INTRODUCTION

DC Circuit Breakers (DC CB) are essential components in DC power grids and technology has been in rapid development in the last 10 years [1][2]. CIGRE had 2 working groups on DC CBs [1] and some DC CBs have been installed in China at 100-500 kV voltages [2].

DC current interruption is much more challenging than with AC systems, and DC CBs typically involve multiple commutation stages in several parallel branches [2]. The implemented DC CB devices are mainly of hybrid type [3]. Recently, a new LC DC CB topology has been developed and demonstrated in the laboratory at 5 kV [4][5]. This DC CB employs a parallel capacitor across the fast main mechanical switch which is constructed with overlapping contacts. It offers several advantages including: early commutation (at the beginning of contact stroke) which improves operating time of DC CB, and use of solely mechanical components that reduces costs. It has been demonstrated that operating time is comparable with commercial hybrid DC CBs that employ costly high-voltage semiconductor valves.

The key technical challenge with LC DC CB is commutation of DC current from fast mechanical switch to a parallel capacitor. Theoretical background for such commutation provides link between mechanical switch (speed of contact separation), commutating current, and parallel capacitance [4]. Further research has studied the success of commutation depending on arc and dielectric properties [6] and various contact design parameters [7]. It is known that parasitics in the commutation path play important role, but previous studies assume ideal commutation circuit and offer only basic theoretical evaluation of the impact of parasitics. The impact of parasitics on high DC current commutation has

been studied in good depth in [8], but only for the DC transfer switch in substations (very low voltage, no current interruption and no commutation in capacitor).

This study aims developing more detailed commutation circuit model and estimating feasibility of commutation with practical Medium Voltage (MV) LC DC CB of around 12 kV. We will verify models using experimental measurements on commercial MV capacitors and bus bars.

II. CAPACITIVE COMMUTATION CIRCUIT

Fig. 1 shows the commutation circuit inside LC DC CB [4], comprising an Ultrafast Disconnector (UFD), series inductor L_{dc} , parallel capacitor C , a surge arrester (SA_c), connected to substation represented by V_{dc} . It is assumed that contact velocity and capacitor size are designed according to LC DC CB design principles in [4]. Parasitic inductance and resistance are not shown but they are present on all cables and with capacitor. When contacts open an arc is formed and arc voltage should be sufficiently high to overcome counter-voltage from parasitics and to commutate current into capacitor. If the UFD current drops below zero arc is interrupted and dielectric barrier is formed between contacts. Once current is commutated to capacitor C the voltage will rise until it is limited by arresters SA_c [4][9]. Then, another LC circuit is formed with series inductor L_{dc} resulting in current reduction which is aided further by SA_c voltage and leads to I_{dc} zero crossing and final interruption by a residual switch (not shown).

The switch with multiple break points is shown in Fig. 1, since design study of 12 kV DC CB indicates that UFD will likely have 6-8 break points [10]. Multiple break points increase contact separation velocity and arc voltage.

Fig. 1. DC current commutation in capacitive circuit.

III. CIRCUIT ANALYTICAL MODEL

To evaluate commutation feasibility, two analytical models are developed. The first model analyses the capacitor discharge required for parameter identification, while the

second captures the RLC behavior during commutation under arc voltage excitation.

A. Capacitor discharge model

Fig. 2 illustrates the simplified model used for identifying parasitics from practical capacitor discharge measurements. The loop includes the test capacitor C , its internal parasitics L_c , R_c and the busbar, and bypass switch path represented by L_p , R_p . The artificial capacitor branch (C_t , R_t) is included for numerical stability (small capacitance and large resistance).

The state-space matrices are:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1/C & 0 & 0; & 1/L_c & -R_c/L_c & -1/L_p & 0; & 0 & 1/C_t & -1/R_t & C_t & -1/C; & 0 & 0 & 1/L_p & -R/L_p \end{bmatrix}, B = \begin{bmatrix} 0; & 0; & 0; & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The state variables are:

$$x(t) = [V_c(t) \ i_c(t) \ V_t(t) \ i_p(t)]^T, \quad (2)$$

with the initial values ($V_{c0}=V_{t0}$):

$$x_0 = [V_{c0} \ 0 \ V_{t0} \ 0]^T. \quad (3)$$

The discharge current and voltage outputs are taken as:

$$i_p(t) = [0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1]^T x(t), \quad V_t(t) = [0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0]^T x(t) \quad (4)$$

Fig. 2. Capacitor discharge model

B. Commutation circuit model

The commutation process is modeled as a 5th order circuit excited by a constant arc voltage V_{arc} , as shown in Fig. 3. The additional loop includes the external supply path L_{dc} , R_{dc} , with the driving voltage V_{dc} that represents substation voltage at the fault instant. The initial current I_{dc0} at the contact separation ($I_{p0}=-I_{dc0}$) is the independent variable in the study. We analyse value for V_{arc} to enable commutation to C ($I_{dc}=-i_c$ and $i_p=0$).

This model expands the study in [5], to include the external branch and more detailed representation of parasitic components. These models were developed in MATLAB.

Fig. 3. Commutation circuit model

IV. MEASUREMENTS OF PARASITIC PARAMETERS

A. Measurement set up

Measurements are performed in the university laboratory with the aim to determine capacitor parasitics for a range of MV capacitors and several busbars. Fig. 4 shows the setup photograph. The capacitor is charged to the initial voltage V_{c0} and then it is discharged through a commercial AC Circuit Breaker (12 kV TAVRIDA). A Testec TT-SI9110 differential voltage probe (V_1) is connected across the capacitor terminals to record the terminal voltage V_t during discharge while a Fluke i1000s high-bandwidth AC current clamp (A_1) is placed on busbars to measure the loop current i_p .

To enhance measurement accuracy, a multimeter (V_2) is connected across the capacitor prior to discharge. This verifies the initial pre-charge voltage and avoids noisy readings at the start of the oscilloscope capture. This is important, as even small errors in the initial voltage reading can lead to significant mismatches when fitting the waveform, considering that parasitic values are small, resulting in high-frequency and underdamped responses.

All waveforms are recorded using a digital oscilloscope with high sampling rate.

B. Test configurations

To identify all parasitic parameters from different parts of the circuit, three test configurations were implemented:

1) *Single Capacitor with Short Bus Bar (Setup 1)*: This provides a baseline measurement of total parasitics, including the internal capacitor elements (L_c , R_c) and short (92 cm) busbar connection paths (L_p , R_p).

2) *Single Capacitor with extended Bus Bar (Setup 2)*: Using the same capacitor as in Setup 1, a longer bus bar is introduced (by adding bus extensions (L_{ex} , R_{ex} of 55 cm) to the short bus bar). By comparing the shift in waveform frequency and damping, the parasitic contribution of the bus bar per unit length can be determined. Additionally, two different busbar sizes are tested.

3) *Parallel Capacitors with Short Bus Bar (Setup 3)*: Two capacitors are connected in parallel to assess parasitic parameters and compare to a single unit.

C. Capacitors and busbars

Eight different commercial capacitors were tested as shown in Fig. 9 in the Appendix, chosen based on their suitability for MV DC applications and with diverse voltage ratings and capacitances.

Fig. 4. Measurement setup for single capacitor with bus extension (setup 2)

Two copper busbars with different geometries (TABLE II. in Appendix) were used to identify inductance and resistance contributions per unit length and geometry, considering realistic layout conditions for MV LC DC circuit breaker.

V. IDENTIFICATION OF PARASITIC PARAMETERS

A. Parameter identification

Parasitic elements were identified by fitting experimental discharge waveforms to the responses from the first state space model. The parameter values for L_c , L_p , R_c , and R_p were manually adjusted to find the best fit to measured waveforms. The initial voltage V_{c0} (also V_{i0}) and capacitance C are known, and C_t , R_t , are kept fixed across all tests.

Setup 1 identifies the total parasitics of capacitors, which are pre-charged to sufficient V_{c0} to keep current below 2000 A, and connected to the bypass switch via busbar-1 (20×3 mm, 92 cm). The total loop inductance ($L_p + L_c$) and resistance ($R_p + R_c$) were found to 814.96 nH and 22.26 m Ω , respectively. Fig. 5 shows the measured responses for 3 capacitors, which also verifies model accuracy.

Setup 2 used the same capacitors but with busbar-1 extended by 55 cm. The additional length increased inductance by 340 nH and resistance by 0.154 m Ω . From this, per-unit busbar parasitics for busbar 1 were estimated as 6.18 nH/cm and 0.0028 m Ω /cm (TABLE II in the Appendix). These were used to calculate the contribution of the 92 cm busbar in Setup 1, which was fixed in the model for all remaining tests, enabling accurate extraction of capacitor-specific parasitics (R_c and L_c).

It is reported that typical high-voltage busbars have inductance around 2 nH/cm [8]. Although our busbars are physically smaller, our extracted values are within a comparable range, lending confidence to the measurement and modeling approach. We need only small busbars in the commutation path since current flows for very short time.

Setup 3 analyzed an 18 kV, 250 μ F capacitor composed of the 150 μ F unit and an additional 100 μ F of the same make in parallel. This configuration increased loop inductance by 276 nH compared to the single 150 μ F case (an undesirable effect), but showed a lower voltage slope during discharge (Fig. 5b, bottom plot), which may reduce voltage stress across contacts and improve dielectric margin during contact travel.

The 150 μ F capacitor tests were repeated with busbar-2 (50×3 mm). Fig. 5c shows measurements for busbar-1 (20×3 mm) and busbar-2 (50×3 mm). As expected, per-unit parasitics dropped and the calculated values were 4.9 nH/cm and 0.00136 m Ω /cm. Fig. 5d also shows results for the 18 kV, 100 μ F capacitor, and it is also seen that the model matches the measured responses well. Among all eight tested capacitors, the 16 kV, 390 μ F and 780 μ F ICAR units have the lowest parasitic values (as shown in TABLE II), making them promising candidates for use in a 12 kV LC DC CB.

VI. FEASIBILITY OF COMMUTATION WITH 12 kV DC CB

A. Analytical Assessment of Commutation Feasibility

The commutation model developed in Section III.B is used to analytically evaluate the peak current I_{p1} and UFD current zero-crossing for all 16-18kV capacitors (100 μ F, 150 μ F, 250 μ F, 390 μ F and 780 μ F), using the identified parasitic parameters. As shown in Fig. 6, larger capacitance

Fig. 5. Comparison of experimental and model discharge responses for 18kV 100 μ F, 150 μ F and 250 μ F (100 μ F+150 μ F) test capacitors

and lower inductance result in higher I_{p1} at lower arc voltages, consistent with prior studies [4][5].

The studies in [10] show that with 12 kV DC CB, the commutating current will be around 4 kA with typical circuit configuration and protection relay parameters, and therefore the peak oscillating current in the commutation circuit should be $I_{p1} > 4$ kA. To assess suitability with some practical margins, the arc voltage required to commutate 4.5 kA fault current is calculated for each capacitor using both busbars. Results are presented in TABLE I. The 780 μ F capacitor provides the lowest values, requiring only 168 V with busbar-1 and 159 V with busbar-2. The previous studies have indicated that electrode fall (at zero contact separation distance) will be around 15-17 V [4][8],[11], and will increase as contact distance increases, approximately doubling at 5 mm distance. This means approximately 8-10

break points are needed to achieve successful commutation with small gap.

The other capacitors require arc voltages exceeding 230 V, however they may be used for interrupting lower currents (1-2 kA load switch application as an example). This highlights the importance of capacitor sizing and parasitic minimization in developing commercial MV DC CB. It is also noted that the commutation voltage can be achieved using other means, as an example using low-voltage semiconductor switch with arrester as demonstrated in [5].

Fig. 6. Arc voltage versus commutating current with all 16-18kV capacitors

TABLE I. ARC VOLTAGE REQUIRED TO COMMULATE 4.5 kA

Description	Required Arc Voltage (V_{arc}) [V]	
	Busbar-1 (20x3 mm)	Busbar-2 (50x3 mm)
16 kV 390 μ F	231	218
16 kV 780 μ F	168	159
18 kV 100 μ F	492	470
18 kV 150 μ F	417	398
18 kV 250 μ F	337	314

To assess performance across a wider range of operating conditions, arc voltage was computed for fault currents from 2 kA to 6 kA, as shown in Fig. 7a-b). The results show feasibility of commutating large currents with equipment of low voltage in the range 200-600V.

Fig. 7. Arc voltage versus commutating current with busbar-1 and -2

B. Time-Domain Commutation Analysis

The commutation circuit model from Fig. 3 was used to analyze commutation dynamics under realistic parasitics, arc voltage and system conditions. The external driving voltage

is set to $V_{dc}=12$ kV, with circuit parameters $L_{dc} = 4$ mH and $R_{dc} = 10$ m Ω . Parasitics for busbar-1 were used in all cases.

Fig. 8a) and b) show capacitor voltage V_c and switch current i_p responses for two 16 kV (100 μ F, 150 μ F) and two 18 kV (390 μ F, 780 μ F) capacitors. Each case uses the minimum arc voltage previously computed in TABLE I.

For all configurations, current is expected to successfully transfer from the bypass switch to the capacitor branch, as indicated by zero crossing in i_p (bottom plots in Fig. 8a-b).

The arcing time (time to first zero crossing) is of importance as it contributes to wearing of contacts and heat dissipation. It is seen to increase with capacitance, ranging from 9.24 μ s (100 μ F) to 23.4 μ s (780 μ F), which are within the arcing duration of typical disconnector designs [4]. The 150 μ F and 390 μ F cases achieve commutation in 10 and 17 μ s, respectively due to reduced damping.

Higher-capacitance cases show reduced voltage slope, which improves dielectric margin across moving contacts.

These results confirm that all four capacitors can achieve successful commutation assuming UFD achieves arc voltage from TABLE I. Among all test capacitors the 390 μ F and 780 μ F capacitors provide the best performance margin, making them strong candidates for 12 kV LC DC CB implementation without auxiliary forcing circuits.

Fig. 8. Commutation with 16-18kV capacitors and calculated arc voltages.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study evaluated the feasibility of passive commutation to capacitive branch in a 12 kV LC DC circuit breaker. The parasitic parameters were extracted from discharge tests on eight commercial capacitors and two busbar configurations. Busbar parasitics were found to be 6.18 nH/cm

and 0.0028 mΩ/cm for a 20×3 mm copper bar and reduced by approximately 21% and 51%, respectively for a 50×3 mm bar.

Time-domain simulations confirmed successful commutation in all tested cases, with current zero crossings occurring within 9–24 μs. The 390 μF and 780 μF capacitors exhibited the lowest arc voltage requirements (under 170 V for 4.5 kA) and the lowest voltage slopes, offering the best margin for safe MV DC CB design. These results demonstrate that 12 kV LC DC CBs might be implemented using passive commutation but depending on the performance of practical UFD and the required safety margins.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project has received funding from Horizon Europe under the grant agreement no 101135484 (MISSION project), and UK partner from UKRI grant agreement 10070225.

The authors are thankful to technicians from the School of Engineering for support with test system and measurements.

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APPENDIX I. Tested capacitors and busbars

Fig. 9. 8 tested capacitors and 2 busbars

TABLE II. COPPER BUS BAR PARAMETERS

	Busbar-1	Busbar-2
Material	Copper	
Width (cm)	2	5
Thickness (cm)	0.3	
Short Bus Length (cm)	92	
Length of bus extension (cm)	55	

APPENDIX II. Estimated values for capacitor and busbar parasitics

TABLE III. ESTIMATED BUS BAR PARAMETERS PER UNIT LENGTH

Description	Estimated Parameters	
	Busbar-1 (20x3mm)	Busbar-2 (50x3mm)
Inductance (nH/cm)	6.17	4.9
Resistance (mΩ/cm)	0.0028	0.00136

TABLE IV. ESTIMATED VALUES FOR CAPACITOR AND BUSBAR PARASITICS

Description	Capacitor Parameters		Busbar Parameters			
	Lc [nH]	Rc [mΩ]	Lex [nH]	Rex [mΩ]	Lp [nH]	Rp [mΩ]
18kV 100μF (ZEE SILKO) capacitor 62.2kg (410x200x470mm)	296.44	19.5	0	0	568.56	0.2576
18kV 150μF (ZEE SILKO) capacitor 67.4kg (410x240x520mm)	246.4	22	0	0	568.56	0.2576
18kV 150μF (ZEE SILKO) capacitor with extended bus connection 67.4kg (410x240x520mm)	246.4	22	340	0.154	568.56	0.2576
18kV 250μF (150uF and 100uF (ZEE SILKO) capacitors in parallel).	183.2	10.37	340	0.154	568.56	0.2576
10kV 300μF (Vishay Electronic GmbH) capacitor 65.6kg (350x245x655mm)	350	14.2	0	0	568.56	0.2576
16kV 390μF (ICAR) capacitor 81.4kg (405x344x410mm)	155	9.6	0	0	568.56	0.2576
6.5kV 400μF (General Atomics Electromagnetics) capacitor 23.1kg (354x183x280mm)	360	27	0	0	568.56	0.2576
1.3kV 590μF (Cornell Dubilier) capacitor 1.8kg (D116x150mm)	100	14	0	0	568.56	0.2576
16kV 780μF (ICAR) capacitor 135.1kg (399x333x758mm)	170	7.5	0	0	568.56	0.2576
900V 2100μF (KEMET) capacitor 3.3kg (D118x274mm)	135	4.5	0	0	568.56	0.2576
With 50x3 mm busbars						
18kV 150μF (ZEE SILKO) capacitor with 50x3mm short bus connection	246.4	22	0	0	568.56	0.2576
18kV 150μF (ZEE SILKO) capacitor with 50x3mm extended busbar	246.4	22	270	0.075	480	0.1029